

Envirotyping: characterizing crop growing environment using soil, weather and management data

Problem

Crop genotypes interact with their environment, which is influenced by soil type and weather, and are affected by the management systems used for their cultivation. To understand why a crop has performed in a particular way and to allow comparison of this performance across multiple locations, it is necessary to characterize the growing environment.

Solution

Envirotyping can show how environmental factors affect plant growth and development. Recording weather conditions, soil parameters and management practices is crucial to accurately characterise the crop growing environment. This information can further be used in crop models to estimate aspects of crop performance that are more difficult to measure, such as crop water use (IRRIGUIDE, ADAS) and nitrogen uptake (CHN, ARVALIS). See figure 1 and 2 for examples.

Principle data inputs

Weather

Rainfall, temperature, solar radiation, humidity, wind speed

Soil

Topsoil depth, subsoil depth to rock, texture in the different horizons, pH, soil organic matter, nutrient concentrations (e.g., P, K and Mg), water holding capacity, bulk density, stone content, total nitrogen, calcium carbonate content, maximum rooting depth

Field

Location (longitude and latitude), altitude, previous crop, sowing and harvest dates, crop type, nutritional inputs, dates of main developmental stages, irrigation, crop protection management information

Quality of the data determines model quality

The quality of the data will determine how well the interaction between genotype, environment and management can be assessed. For instance,

Applicability box

Theme: Envirotyping

Relevance: Characterizing the growing environment of crops

Best in: All crops and environments

Measured traits:

Rainfall (mm), temperature (°C), solar radiation (TJ/m²), soil texture, soil depth (m), soil organic matter (%), soil pH and nutrients, crop management practices and field history

Required time: Required time includes taking soil samples and lab analysis, collating weather- and field-history data. This amounts to around 1 day (8 hours) per site.

localized rainfall data, recent soil nutrient reports, soil organic matter and pH information alongside representative soil sampling methods are essential for an accurate evaluation.

Practical recommendations

- For comparability, ensure the same standardized soil analysis methods across environments as practices can vary.
- Maintain uniform units of measurement across environments to facilitate comparison.
- Soil water status can be monitored during the crop growing season using tools such as soil moisture sensors and tensiometers.

Figure 1. Example of CHN model output variables to characterize crop growth conditions (Variety : Anvergur, Location: Ouzouer, year : 2022). These outputs can be used to assess water and nitrogen stress during the growing period. The "Water stress factor" and "Nitrogen stress factor" quantify how much water and nitrogen limitations affect plant growth, respectively. The lower the stress factor, the greater the negative impact on the actual biomass production relative to its potential under ideal conditions. *The temperature sum measures the cumulative heat available over time, above 0°C, that contributes to the growth and development of crops.

Figure 2. Comparison between measured (·) and modelled (—) soil water change for a potato crop in an irrigated and unirrigated scenario using the IRRIGUIDE model. Vertical bars represent the standard error for measured values. IRRIGUIDE is a field-scale model of evaporation, transpiration and drainage, originally designed for irrigation scheduling. This model calculates daily soil moisture deficit using weather data, soil condition and modelled crop development. The figure illustrates that the modelled soil moisture deficit is similar to what was measured. Taken from: Bailey and Spackman, 1996.

Further information

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- Le Bris, X., Soenen, B., Laberdesque, M., Gouache, D., Lorgeou, J., Piquemal, B. (2015). "CHN", a crop model to add value to phenotyping and approach genetic variation for RUE and WUE. In: Recent progress in drought tolerance: from genetics to modelling, 8-12 June 2015, Montpellier, France. Available at: [researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net).

About this practice abstract and Root2Resilience

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